

Mapping the Global Flow of Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Composites and Supply Chain Energy Requirements

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Motivation to Decarbonize FRPC Production

Fiber-reinforced polymer composites (FRPCs) are becoming increasingly used across transport, electronics, wind energy and other sectors

However, their production comes with environmental problems such as:

- High energy and emission intensities
- Low recycling rate at end-of-life (~2%)
- High process scrap rate (e.g., *prepreg cutting waste* ~ 30-40%) with most scrap landfilled

Aim: understanding decarbonization priorities within the global FRPC supply chain

Fig. 1. Cumulative energy demand of materials

Fig. 2. Global recycling rate of materials

Life Cycle Analysis for Process-level Impacts

Life cycle analysis (LCA)

- Most common method
- Focus on process-level impacts
- Examples findings for LCAs on FRPC:
 - A CFRP automotive part need ~ 4 times the **primary energy** of a steel one (Das, 2011; Ghosh et al., 2021)
 - High **resource depletion, water consumption** (Wegmann et al., 2022; Walker and Thies, 2022)
 - Bio-based composites need double the **land use** of C/GFRP and steel (Walker and Thies, 2022)

Limitations of LCA

Lacking material quantity considerations (intensity vs. demand), limiting guidance for research and investment prioritization

Table 1. An example of quantity & impact

	Glass fiber	Carbon fiber
Global production	~6,000 kt	~1,00 kt
Primary energy intensity	~22 MJ/kg	~350 MJ/kg

Material Flow Analysis - Environmental Impacts With Material Quantity Considerations

Material flow analysis (MFA)

- Characterizes how a given material is transformed through a supply chain
- Enables the impact assessment across a supply chain on an equal footing

Existing MFA on FRPC

- J. Rybicka et al. (2015) mapped 4 different processes to capture FRPC mfg. scrap flows
- Shuaib et al., (2015) mapped the UK CFRP and GFRP supply chains
- Hamid et al. (2025) mapped global composites waste from wind turbine blades

Current Gap

There is only process-level, sectorial and regional, low-resolution supply-chain-level MFA on FRPC

To identify decarbonization priorities, we conducted an MFA on the global FRPC supply chain

This research: Material flow analysis (MFA) + Energy Analysis to Reveal FRPC Decarbonization Priorities

Key contributions: using MFA to quantify the material efficiency and energy demand in global fiber reinforced polymer composite supply chain

1. Model the **mass** flows and their uncertainties in the global FRP composite supply chain with Bayesian inference
2. Quantify the **primary energy** attributable to FRP materials, processes and end-use sectors
3. Identify the **decarbonization opportunities** in the global FRPC production system

Fig. 3. Scope of this material flow analysis.

Methodology

Material Flow Analysis - Model Structure

Fig. 4. An example MFA network (Dong et al., 2023)

Material Flow Analysis - Data Collection

Data collection

- Material production and demand - market reports (e.g., JEC), research articles, OEM websites
- Primary energy intensities - Ecoinvent 3 database, LCA studies, industry reports (e.g., JCMA)

Data Format	Examples
Mass Flow Data	
Flow values (in kt)	The amount of aramid paper used in aramid honeycomb production is 3.4 kt globally.
Transfer coefficients (0 – 100%) (e.g., Scrap & recycling rates)	The process yield for GFRP prepreg production is 93%.
Technical coefficients (0 – 100%) (e.g., Fiber/matrix mass ratios)	The typical fiber fraction of open molded parts are 50 wt.% (40 vol.%). 32% of the composite products in marine application were manufactured via spray-up in 2022.
Percentage share of any process in a sum of processes (0 – 100%)	The volume of composite products in construction accounts for 26% of the total composite market in 2022 (JEC, 2023).
Node throughputs (in kt)	The volume of global composites market in construction applications was 3.3 mt in 2022 (JEC, 2023).
Sum of nodes (in kt)	The total volume of thermoset composites in the market is 7.8 Mt in 2022 (JEC, 2023).
Energy Intensity Data	
Primary energy intensities (in MJ/kg)	The primary energy intensity of glass fiber direct roving is 28 MJ/kg.

MFA Data Noise Modelling Using Pedigree Matrix

Why modelling data noise?

- Data are not 100% reliable or correct
- Enable transparent decision-making

Pedigree Matrix Approach

- For a given data, **assign data quality scores** (1-4, smaller numbers mean higher quality) for **5 data quality metrics** (reliability, completeness, temporal correlation, geographical correlation, other correlation)
- Calculate: **coefficient of variation (CV)** for normal distribution or **uncertainty parameter (U)** for lognormal distribution using:

For each quality metric: $CV_i = a * e^{b*(score_i-1)}; U_i = 1 + \frac{CV_i}{100}$

Total noise for data: $CV_{total} = \sqrt{\sum CV_i^2}; U_{total} = \exp(\sqrt{\sum \ln(U_i)^2})$

$a_{not\ sensitive} = 0.375; a_{medium\ sensitive} = 0.75; a_{highly\ sensitive} = 1.5; b = 1.105$

Uncertainty Quantification via Bayesian Inference

Data inconsistencies and uncertainties

- Discrepancies across data sources
- Various forms
- Data scarcity

Bayesian inference (BI)

BI uses **probability distributions** to represent data record with uncertainties and enables **updating of model parameter (material flow) uncertainties** as more data is collected (Lupton and Allwood, 2018)

Results – Global Flow of FRP Composites in 2024 (in Million tons)

Key information: material throughputs (thickness of flows), data uncertainty (color of flows), scrap flows

Material Efficiency of the Global FRPC Supply Chain

Scrap primarily come from

- **Thermoset processes** (>50%)
- **High-throughput processes** (injection molding, TP compound production, compound production)
- **Manual processes or semi-manual processes** (spray-up, hand layup, vacuum assisted resin infusion VARI etc.)

Fig. 5. Manufacturing scrap profile
(TS: thermoset; TP: thermoplastic; PPG: prepreg)

Primary Energy Demands of FRPC Materials and Processes

Energy Hotspots

- **Resin**, especially **unsaturated polyester (UPE)**
- **Autoclave curing**
- **Glass and natural fibers** (vs. carbon)

Fig. 6. (a) Total primary energy demand and (b) primary energy demand by material and processes.

Attributing Primary Energy to Processes/Sectors

Fig. 7. Primary energy attributable to mfg. processes

Fig. 8. Primary energy attributable to end-use sectors

Conclusions

This study provides a new perspective on the material efficiency and energy demand distributions within the global FRPC supply chain.

Key take-aways

- **Low-value materials** and **high-throughput processes** have **large material and energy footprints** and **should be prioritized for decarbonization efforts.**
- **Resin production** accounts for **most primary energy requirement.** Substitution with bio-based options can potentially have a great impact on supply chain decarbonization.
- **Manufacturing scrap generation is significant** and scrap recycling remains minimal. **Yield improvement should focus on high-throughput processes manual processes.**

Thank You

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